

RELATIONS OF NATIONALITY, LANGUAGE AND CULTURE.

Musulmonov Shabon Bahodir o'g'li

Termiz State University University,
Faculty of Foreign Philology, 3st year student.

Annotation: Nationality is the identity of a person they were born into while ethnicity is the identity of a subgroup they come from. People of the same nation can have different ethnicities, and people of the same ethnicity can belong to different nations. Awareness of cultural relativism allows one to break free from the misunderstood attachment to one's culture that affects one's perceptions and perspectives on the world. It also helps to understand different cultures. Using the cultural relativism view leads to the perspective that no culture is superior to any other when compared to systems of morality, law, politics, etc. It is a notion that cultural norms and values acquire their meaning in a particular societal context.

Keywords: ethnicity, nationality, inheritance, ancestral, dynamic, morality, culture. As with any culture, members of an ethnic group share certain beliefs, values, habits, customs, and norms because of their common background. They define themselves as different and special based on cultural characteristics. This distinction may arise from language, religion, historical experience, geographic location, kinship, or race. Hallmarks of an ethnic group can include a collective name, a belief in common ancestry, a sense of solidarity, and a connection to a specific territory that may or may not belong to the group. [1]

According to Fredrik Barth (1969), ethnicity occurs when people claim a certain ethnic identity for themselves and are defined by others as bearers of this identity. Ethnicity means identifying with and belonging to an ethnic group and being excluded from certain other groups because of that membership. Ethnic feelings and related behavior vary in intensity within ethnic groups and countries

and over time. A change in the meaning attached to an ethnic identity may reflect political changes or changes in the individual life cycle (young people give up their ethnic origins or old people reclaim them). Cultural differences can be associated with ethnicity, class, region, or religion. Individuals often have more than one group identity. People may (depending on circumstances) be loyal to their neighborhood, school, city, state or province, region, nation, continent, religion, ethnic group, or interest group. [2]. In a complex society like the United States or Canada, people are constantly negotiating their social identity. One learner notes that ethnicity is understood as an inherited status that depends on the society in which a person lives. Belonging to a subgroup of the population with similar physical or social characteristics are the states of it. Furthermore, ethnicity is a person's ethnic identity discovered through traits based on ancestry. Ancestry-based traits denote the traits related to ancestry, i.e. genetic traits, along with cultural or historical inheritance. Ethnicity is the category of people referred to as an ethnic group who are distinguished from others because of their ancestral, social, and national heritage. Shared traditions, history, language or dialect, culture, behavior, religion, physical appearance, and some other factors e.g. B. It is the quality of a person's individuality that leads to their integration into a nation.

In addition, nationality means the identity of a large group of people who are legally connected to a specific place of residence and personally connected because they were born there. It intensifies the country in which a person is born and a citizen. For example, Uzbek, American, British, Indian, etc. Citizenship law deals with its determination and determines the states for obtaining citizenship. However, it can be owned by birth, inheritance, or naturalization. The state, the authority over the person, is thereby modified, it transfers to the person as well as the defense of the state. The rights and powers of the state and its officials vary in different countries. The source of patriotism and self-sacrifice is supplied by it since it is psychological. There are several differences between nationality and

ethnicity, which I will discuss below.

1. A person's ethnic identity is denoted by ethnicity based on ancestry characteristics and cultural heritage. However, nationality shows a personal connection to the nation as it is an individual affiliation to the nation.

2. Dialect, culture, diet, dress style, race, and physical appearance can be determined by ethnicity. In contrast, a person's nationality can be determined by their country of origin.

3. Heredity and descent are described by ethnic status. On the other hand, nationality is the legal identity that only refers to a person born in the country.

4. While ethnicity arises from a person's ethnic background, nationality is intensified by geographic location.

In short, a researcher must have sufficient knowledge of ethnicity and nationality. Identity formation and development have a great relationship with them. Put simply, nationality is the identity of a person into which they were born, while ethnicity is the identity of a subgroup they come from. Individuals of the same nation can belong to different ethnicities, as we discussed in our first example, and likewise, individuals of the same ethnicity can belong to respective nations. To be clearer, a person born in Uzbekistan and resident in the United States only has Uzbek citizenship but not American citizenship. If a person in the United States was born into an Uzbek family, then that person would have an Uzbek, not an American, ethnicity. Ethnicity is inevitably the condition that alters heredity and descent. However, nationality is the legitimate identity bestowed only on a person born in the country.

Culture is defined as the way of life of a group of individuals. Arts, beliefs, and institutions passed from one generation to the next can be included in this way. Almost all cultures are learned, dynamic, integrated, symbolic, and shared. Cultures are vital in society as they bring social and economic benefits. Cultural relativism is the concept that every culture is different from one other, as well as

distinguishing their moral structures and relational frameworks. Meanwhile, cultural relativism refers to understanding a culture based on its reputation, not judging it for itself. The idea and goal of cultural relativism are to help people perceive and understand other cultures that are not their own. Cultural relativism is important because it helps to appreciate the ways of life of other people around the world. [3]To explain, I can say that cultural relativism is a moral theory that describes a person's relative and appropriate culture. Thus, different ethical positions in different cultures are addressed with this concept. As I clarified above, this concept is a belief that no culture is superior to the other in politics and morality. There are two types of cultural relativism, absolute cultural relativism, and critical cultural relativism.

Absolute cultural relativism holds that no matter how strange and dangerous activities are practiced within one culture, they should not be questioned or analyzed by other cultures. On the other hand, critical cultural relativism asks questions about cultural activities, the reasons for their practices, who accepts them, and what purpose they serve. Cultural relativism avoids hasty judgments and is the principle of looking at and evaluating the practices of a culture from its point of view. [4]

There are many examples of cultural relativism, one of which is food choices. It's the best example of how everyone has become more patient with foods from foreign cultures. In the past, people had to ignore some foods, but almost no one judges a person by their food choices. Ultimately, cultural relativism allows the person to clarify their moral code without strengthening the moral code of other people. Everyone is different in such a society. These differences create equality because everyone can determine their explanation of success. Every culture has its way of relativizing. There are many cultural relativisms in Uzbek culture in their holidays, weddings, and other ceremonies. Let's take an Uzbek wedding as an example, which is different in different regions of Uzbekistan. For example, there

is no early labor protection in Khorezm, but there is in Tashkent and some other regions. In the afternoon, Osh is cooked in Khorezm while the bride says goodbye to her relatives. Relatives and friends of the groom come to the bride's house and take the bride to Osh in the afternoon. Then the relatives and friends of the bride go to the groom's house and prepare for the wedding celebration, which will take place in the evening. The Uzbek wedding ceremony is celebrated by several people. Many guests are invited. They eat, dance, and wish the bride and groom and their parents all the best. At the end of the party, the groom's parents are invited to the wedding location and thank all visitors, and wish both the newlyweds and the guests all the best. Kelin Salom's wedding takes place the next day. The bride bows to all of the groom's relatives and friends. Chuchvara (Barak in Khorezm) is cooked on this day and guests are invited to eat it. All guests congratulate the newlyweds and present them with many gifts. In short, awareness of cultural relativism allows one to break free from the misunderstood bondage of their culture, which affects their perceptions and perspectives on the world. It also helps to understand different cultures. Using the cultural relativism view leads to the perspective that no culture is superior to any other when compared to systems of morality, law, politics, etc. It's a notion that cultural norms and values get their meaning in a particular social context.

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